

ASSESSMENT OF HEALTH RISK KNOWLEDGE AND ATTITUDE ASSOCIATED WITH SACHET WATER CONSUMPTION AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN THE ENUGU EDUCATION ZONE

Emesih Kelechi Micheal, MSc. HKHE, ESUT

E-mail: Kelechi.micheal.96@gmail.com

Phone Number: 08104864447

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17830878>

ABSTRACT: This study assessed the knowledge and attitude of secondary school students about health risk associated with sachet water consumption in the Enugu Education Zone. The study was guided by two research purposes and two research questions. This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population for the study was 32,185 and the Taro Yamane formula was adopted to establish a sample of 395 students. Multistage sampling technique comprising proportionate, purposive, and simple random sampling was used to determine the respondents. Self-structured questionnaire which was validated by three experts was used as an instrument for data collection. Data collection was conducted through direct visitation of the sampled school to administer the instrument. The collected data were analyzed using the mean and standard deviation. The analysis showed that the low knowledge (2.42) of the health risks of sachet water, which significantly predicts their risky attitudes (3.36), with higher knowledge associated with safer behaviors. The study concluded that there was low level of knowledge regarding the health risks associated with sachet water consumption among students and this low knowledge significantly influences their attitudes, as evidenced by the moderate negative relationship and regression results showing that higher knowledge is associated with safer behaviors. Hence, it is hoped that related stakeholders will endorse conservative efforts to alleviate this health issue. The researcher recommends that schools should monitor the provision and storage of water sachets sold in school premises to ensure that they are not contaminated. They should educate students and parents on the importance of safe water consumption to improve their knowledge and alertness toward unsafe sachet water.

Keywords: Knowledge, Attitude, Health Risk, and Sachet Water

Introduction

Water is one of the essential natural substances that play a crucial role in the maintenance of proper body functions and overall health. According to Emerenini (2020), water is a transparent fluid that forms streams, lakes, oceans, and rain and is the major constituent of the fluids of organisms. Zumdahl (2020) viewed water as an inorganic, odorless, tasteless, and transparent substance made up of hydrogen and oxygen existing in gaseous, liquid, and solid states. This inorganic substance covers a large area of the Earth's surface and is required in numerous human activities. Thus, the World Health Organization (WHO, 2018) defined water as a

"universal solvent" and a fundamental resource for human health and well-being. Thereby affirming that water is a substance that is required in all human activities, without which life may cease to exist. In support of this assertion, Okeh (2021) affirmed that human existence on the Earth's surface would have been impossible without the presence of water.

Water is an important element required in all human activities, including physiological functions of the body. This is because the presence of water in the human body is associated with the maintenance and appropriate physiological function of the body systems. According to Water Science School (2019), up to 60% of the human body systems. The same author further reveals that the brain and heart are composed of 73% water, the lungs 83%, the skin 64%, the muscles and kidneys 79%, and even the bones are watery (31%). Consequently, individuals must consume a certain amount of water to survive daily. Generally, an adult male needs about 3 liters (3.2 quarts) per day while an adult female needs about 2.2 liters (2.3 quarts) per day (Water Science School, 2019). This submission suggests that drinking water is important for individuals to ensure that their bodies function at an appropriate rate. In addition, Okeh (2021) affirmed that water intake has a significant impact on maintaining proper body temperature, regulating metabolism and promoting nutrient digestion and absorption. Water is a vital nutrient to the life of every cell. It acts first as a building material, regulates the internal body temperature by sweating and respiration and helps in food metabolism and transportation of nutrient in the bloodstream. However, Miner, Tagurum, Hassan, Afolaranmi, Bello, Dakhin and Zoakah, (2016) found that access to safe drinking water is a global concern that continues to receive attention. The same author further adds that in most cases, the problem is not water availability but the inability to obtain quality water. This shows that there may be insufficient provision of safe water supply in Nigerian communities. Ojekunle, Ojekunle, Eruola, Oyebanji, Olatunde, Amujo, Sangowusi, Adekitan, and Taiwo, (2015) suggested that most Nigeria utilize boreholes, rain water or water from streams and rivers in order to handle their daily activities such as washing, bathing and cleaning. However, due to concerns that this water source may not be safe for drinking, sachet water was introduced as an alternative source of water for drinking.

Sachet water is commonly known in Nigeria as 'pure water'. Sachet water refers to 50 cl sealed plastic sleeves of purified drinking water, which is widely used in most West Africa countries due to its affordability and general perception of quality (Wright, Dzodzomenyo, Fink, Wardrop, Aryeetey, Adanu & Hill, 2016). According to Miner, Tagurum, Hassan, Afolaranmi, Bello, Dakhin and Zoakah (2016), sachet water may involve the treatment of well water, rain water and borehole water and in some case pipe-borne water, to make them suitable for drinking. Approximately 70% of Nigerian adults consume this water. A large percentage of people in Nigeria consume sachet water as the major source of drinking water. However, Kusa and Williams (2022) raised concern that sachet water may contain heavy metals, nonmetals, and ions and biological contamination. Heavy metals such as; lead, cadmium, and mercury, can be toxic even in small amounts and cause various health problems, including damage to the nervous system, kidneys, and liver. Onwumere (2023) affirmed that sachet or packaged water, which is the major means of drinking water in Nigeria, is not exempted of deadly organisms because it is a microbial substance. The same author also revealed that polythene bags, which are

used as a package or sachet for pure water are made of synthetic petroleum which may deteriorates the water in them, because the polythene bags are weather-susceptible. Therefore, sun rays or heat may melt some of the synthetic petroleum into the water, making it dangerous for consumption (Onwumere, 2023). This report suggested that majority of the sachet water which are exposed to sun rays and hawked in every part of Nigeria, may be dangerous to health if consumed often. Supporting this assertion, Nwokolo (2023), stated that when exposed to sunlight, bisphenol A or BPA, a chemical that is used to make the sachet for sachet water may pose a serious threat to health as it may lead to health problems such as hypertension, heart attack, coronary artery heart disease, angina, and even changes in blood pressure. Hassan, Musa and Mohammed (2016) revealed that water treatment facilities may be lacking or have been dilapidated because of poor maintenance, which may result in sachet water production contamination.

Apart from possible contamination due to exposure to sunlight and treatment, sachet water is also susceptible to osmotic reaction due to the polythene bags used in packaging the water (Nwokolo, 2023). Therefore,if sachet waters are stored at a particular place over time, the particles in the surrounding might contaminate the sachet water through osmotic movements,exposing consumers to numerous health problems. Moreover, in a Radiological investigation of 35 brands of the most popularly used sachet drinking water in Nigeria, Aladeniyi, Olowookere,Khandaker and Alsufyani (2022) found that sachet water may cause cancer due to the presence of radionuclides (^{226}Ra and ^{228}Ra) which were found to exceed the acceptable limits of 0.1 mSv y^{-1} and 10^{-7} respectively. This implies a non-negligible carcinogenic health hazard may exist due to the intake of the surveyed drinking water, especially for the lactating babies (0–1) teenagers (12–17) years. However, despite these concerns, the researcher observed that individuals,especially secondary school students,simply assume that sachet water is clean for consumption. The normal practice of sachet water consumers,especially students,is to simply purchase and drink, with little effort made to ascertain the level of purity of the sachet water while neglecting the possible health risk of knowingly or unknowinglyconsuming sachet water. From the foregoing, it is argued that sachet water in Nigeria may not be justify its popular name “pure water”, because there are possibly numerous negative conditions that can expose consumers of sachet water to health problems during the production of sachet water or otherwise. This also highlights a major concern because it demonstrate that school-aged children who are seen as the “battle of future development” may knowingly or unknowingly contract treatable and sometimes untreatable due to sachet water consumption. This may further worsen the county’s already high prevalence of disease and healthcare strain. Thereby raising questions about whether individual’s especially secondary school students in Nigeria, possess adequate knowledge on the possible health risk of sachet water consumption.

Knowledge refers to the basic understanding of facts related to a given variable or phenomenon. According to Coffey (2017) knowledge is the awareness and understanding of particular aspects of reality, and this requires accurate information, justification through evidence, and reasoning that is justified as true belief. This means that the level of knowledge of health risk of sachet water consumption would successfully highlight the level of information the individual possess on the possible adverse health effects of consuming sachet water. Nnaji

(2021) affirmed that the level of knowledge of a health problem may assist in determining an individual's or group's strength and weakness towards effective health behavioral change. However, empirical evidence that examined the knowledge of health risk of sachet water consumption in secondary schools in Enugu State is limited. Moreover, based on the health belief model (Rosenstock, 1974), it can be argued that an examination of the level of knowledge may be inconclusive without an evaluation of attitude towards health risk of sachet water consumption because the level of knowledge of individuals would significantly influence their attitude towards health promotion.

Just like the two sides of a coin, knowledge and attitude are complimentary for health promotion and behavioral change. Attitude is a learned disposition or the tendency to respond positively or negatively to an idea, person, object, or situation (İnceoğlu, 2010). This means that attitude represents a person's evaluative judgments or feelings towards something and can influence their behavior and decision-making. Therefore, a positive attitude towards sachet water consumption would lead to a reduction in the health risk exposure of sachet water consumers. Conversely, a negative attitude that condones or overlooks the health risk of sachet water exposure could lead to an increased prevalence of disease and other associated illness (Sridhar, Okareh and Mustapha, 2020). In other words, some students may feel that sachet water is convenience and affordability for consumption during school hours. Sachet water is also easier to carry and dispose of than larger water bottles. However, Okeh (2021), found that some students may express concerns about the health risk of water consumption; however, due to numerous barriers it may be impossible for them to practice safer alternative. Thus, attitude towards health risk factors of sachet water consumption, especially among students in secondary schools in Enugu Education Zone, are important because they can shape perceptions and actions related to the practice of safe water consumption while promoting healthily living.

Secondary schools are organization where formal education occur. According to the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), secondary education is an important stage where students acquire advanced knowledge and skills to prepare them for higher education or the workforce (UNESCO, 2021). Secondary school students in this study refer to individuals between the ages of 12 and 17 who attend secondary schools in Enugu Education Zone. Secondary school students are an important variable in this study because they constitute the highest risk group of water-related diseases. According to Premium Times (2023), over 26.5 million children in Nigeria are extremely vulnerable to water-related diseases and antimicrobial resistance. In addition, UNICEF (2023), reported that the acute lack of potable water in Nigeria has numerous negative consequences on the health and growth of school-aged children. According to the World Health Organization (2017), poor drinking water is believed to cause 4.0% of all deaths and 5.7% of ill health in the Nigeria. Previous studies have shown that contaminated drinking-water is estimated to cause more than 500 000 diarrheal deaths each year. These submissions suggest that there is a high prevalence of water related-diseases among students, and the diseases may have been transmitted through sachet water consumption. The extent of knowledge and attitude regarding the health risks associated with sachet water consumption among secondary school students can provide insight into the level of understanding about the potential health hazards

posed by sachet water consumption. Thus, this study examined the knowledge and attitude of secondary school students in Enugu Education Zone regarding health risk associated with sachet water consumption.

Statement of the Problem

Owing to the lack of basic amenities in Nigeria, including the lack of pipe-borne water in numerous part of the country, sachet water is produced to ensure the adequate availability of safe water for consumption. Therefore, it is expected that sachet water will be treated and free from impurity and other diseases for safe consumption of sachet water. However, numerous health risk factors have been associated with the consumption of sachet water, including the dangerous chemical composition of the sachet and possible water contamination during storage.

Nevertheless, students in secondary schools in Enugu Education Zone continued to consume sachet water in schools with little or no regards towards the risk associated with the consumption of sachet water. The researcher observed that students simply purchase and drink sachet water without regards for where the water came from or the sanitary procedures associated with its storage before sales. The common attitude suggests that they erroneously believe that sachet water is definitely free of impurity and safe for drinking. In addition, the majority of students reported being absent from school or hospitalized due to water-related diseases, such as typhoid among others. Based on concerned that the observed diseases may be related to sachet water consumption. The researcher felt puzzled about whether students are aware of the health risk associated with the consumption of sachet water and why they continue to consume sachet water if they are aware of the risks. Are students knowledgeable on the health risk associated with consumption of sachet water? If they do or do not possess adequate knowledge or otherwise, what exactly is their attitude towards the consumption of sachet water? Hence the study examined the level of knowledge and attitude towards health risk associated with sachet water consumption among secondary school students in Enugu Education Zone.

Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of this study is to determine the level of knowledge and attitude of secondary school students in Enugu Education Zone regarding the health risks associated with sachet water consumption. Specifically, the study sought to;

1. Determine the level of knowledge of health risks associated with sachet water consumption among secondary school students in the Enugu Education Zone (EEZ).
2. Find out the attitude towards health risks associated with sachet water consumption among secondary school students in the Enugu Education Zone (EEZ).
3. Ascertain the relationship between the knowledge and attitude towards health risks associated with sachet water consumption among secondary school students in the Enugu Education Zone (EEZ).

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study design:

1. What is the knowledge level of secondary school students in the Enugu Education Zone regarding the health risks associated with sachet water consumption?

2. What is the attitude of secondary school students towards health risk associated with sachet water consumption in the Enugu Education Zone?

3. What is the relationship between the knowledge and attitude towards health risks associated with sachet water consumption among secondary school students?

Methods

Design and Setting: The researcher Kelechi Emesih (K.M) employed a descriptive co-relational design to carry out the study using Enugu Education Zone as the setting or Area of the study.

Population: The target population according to Post Primary School Management Board (2021), consisted of 32,185 students (Male, 12,733; Female, 19,452) in 27 public secondary schools in Enugu Education Zone.

Sample and Sampling Technique: The sample size of 395 students was determined using the Taro Yamen formula. K.M used multistage cluster sampling procedure. In the first stage, purposive sampling technique was used to select two LGAs out of three LGAs in the Enugu Education Zone. This was used because the researcher wanted to sample students based on rural and urban location. The same sampling technique was used to sample five secondary schools from the 19 secondary schools in the two LGAs because the researcher aimed to ensure that both male and female had equal chance to participate in the study. Simple random sampling technique of balloting without replacement was used to sample 79 students from each of the 5 sampled schools making it 395 students.

Instrument for data collection: Self structured questionnaire titled “Knowledge and Attitude of Health Risk Associated with Sachet Water Consumption Questionnaire (KAHRASWCQ)” designed by the researchers. The questionnaire was divided into two sections. Section A consisted of the demographic data of the respondents, while section B consisted of statement to elicit information on the knowledge and attitude towards of health risk associated with sachet water consumption. Section B was divided into two clusters. Cluster one had eight items on the knowledge of health risks associated with sachet water consumption, and cluster two had ten items on attitude towards health risks associated with sachet water consumption. The responses options ii a likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA: 4), Agree (A: 3), Disagree (D: 2) and Strongly Disagree (SD: 1). The instrument was validated by three Health Education expert. The experts critically examined the instrument and made useful suggestions before final production. The instrument was considered reliable, with a co-efficiency of 0.79, and was tested with Cronbach Alpha. K.M administered the questionnaire with the help of research assistants on days agreed upon by the researchers, the research assistants, and the secondary schools.

Method of Data Collection: In order to administer the questionnaire, the researcher ensured that the instrument was ethically approved by the school principals. The researcher scheduled appointment with the principal, during which the questionnaire was vetted and approved for the study. The principals also arranged for a school administrator to assist in the sharing and retrieval of the questionnaire instrument. The researcher briefed the school administrators on the research aim and objectives in order to ensure appropriate distribution and collection of data.

Ethical Consideration: The questionnaire was approved by Principals/ Head Teacher of the selected schools. The questionnaire data was based on anonymity as no name or contact information was included. In addition, voluntary participation was ensured by asking the students if they wished to participate in the study before sharing the questionnaire to them.

Data Analysis: After data collection, 35 out of 395 copies of the questionnaire were filled incorrectly; thus, only 360 copies of the questionnaire were used for data analysis. The collected data were analyzed using the descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation and inferential statistics such as t-test and regression. Mean and standard deviation was used for research question one and two while the decision rule was that item with a mean response of 2.5 and above was considered high-level and any mean score below 2.5 is considered low-level. For research question three, t-test and regression was used to determine the significant differences in the responses of the respondents as well as the relationship between knowledge and attitude.

Analysis and Results

Research Question One: What is the knowledge level of secondary school students in the Enugu Education Zone regarding the health risk associated with sachet water consumption among?

Table 1: Mean Distribution of Respondents Knowledge Level of Health Risk Associated with Sachet Water Consumption
n= 360

S/n	Item: The health risk factors of sachet water consumption	VHE 4	HE 3	LL 2	VLL 1	Mean X	SD	Deci
1	Sachet water can cause gastrointestinal infections	170	60	115	15	3.07	0.98	HL
2	Sachet water can lead to typhoid fever	105	104	60	91	2.62	1.15	HL
3	Sachet water can lead to cancer	20	110	130	100	2.14	0.89	LL
4	Sachet water poisoning	86	84	20	110	2.07	1.18	LL
5	Sachet water can cause parasitic infections	102	80	178	0	2.79	0.86	HL
6	Improper sachet water storage can lead health problems	40	106	106	108	2.22	1.00	LL
7	Consuming water sachet without washing your hands can lead to health issues	47	89	124	100	2.23	0.79	LL
8	Exposing sachet water to the sun can cause health problems	60	65	135	100	2.24	1.03	LL
Cluster mean						2.42	0.96	LL

In Table 1, majority of the respondents identified items 1 (3.07), 2 (2.62), and 5 (2.79) as the health risk of sachet water consumption, while the rest of the items were below the average mean of 2.50. The cluster mean of 2.42 suggests that secondary school students in Enugu Education Zone possess a low level of knowledge on the health risk of sachet water, where a the standard deviation is 0.96 indicating a low dispersion of data from the mean.

Research Question Two: What is the attitude of secondary school students in the Enugu Education Zone towards health risks associated with sachet water consumption?

Table 2: Mean Distribution of Attitudes toward Health Risk Associated with Sachet Water Consumption
n= 360

S/n	Item: The following are the attitudes toward the health risks associated with sachet water consumption	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	SD	Deci
		4	3	2	1	X		
9	ignore or underestimate the importance of clean drinking water	290	54	10	6	3.74	0.59	A
10	drink untreated sachet water without proper filtration or purification	236	70	34	20	3.45	0.88	A
11	consume expired or improperly stored sachet water	206	136	18	0	3.52	0.59	A
12	share sachet water with my peers	170	71	114	5	3.13	0.91	A
13	do not wash my hands before handling or consuming sachet water	211	110	39	0	3.48	0.69	A
14	drink sachet water from unverified or unreliable sources	180	76	94	10	3.18	0.92	A
15	rely solely on sachet water for hydration without alternative sources	237	84	29	10	3.52	0.76	A
16	consume sachet water without checking for proper seals or packaging integrity	240	70	40	10	3.50	0.79	A
17	sachet water bags without proper cleaning or disinfection	102	80	178	0	2.79	0.86	A
18	do not dispose of used sachet water improperly,	200	70	70	20	3.25	0.95	A
Cluster mean						3.36	0.79	A

Table 2 shows that, the respondents agreed with all items 9 (3.74), 10 (3.45), 11 (3.52), 12 (3.13), 13 (3.48), 14 (3.18), 16 (3.50), 17 (2.79) and 18 (3.25). Considering that the items were based on negative attitudes towards health risk of sachet water consumption, the cluster mean of 3.36 signifies that secondary school students in the Enugu Education Zone have a poor attitude toward health risk of sachet water consumption.

Research Question Three: What is the relationship between the knowledge and attitude towards health risks associated with sachet water consumption among secondary school students?

Table 3: t-test on relationship between the knowledge and attitude towards health risks associated with sachet water consumption among secondary school students

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	p-value	Sig	Decision
-----------	---	------	----	----	---------	---------	-----	----------

Knowledge	360	2.42	0.96	718	-14.35	P <0.001	0.05	Significant
Attitude	360	3.36	0.79					

The table shows a significant difference exists between students' knowledge and their attitudes. This is evident from the fact that attitude scores (3.36) are significantly higher than knowledge scores (2.42). Since attitude reflects risky behaviors, this means that students demonstrate poor knowledge about the health risks of sachet water but show high-risk attitudes toward consuming sachet water. This inverse relationship suggests that low knowledge contributes to poor attitudes. Specifically, the t-test shows a strong, statistically significant difference between knowledge and attitude indicating that there is an indirect negative relationship which highlights that as knowledge decreases, Risky attitudes increase.

Table 5: Model-Based Regression Using the Correlation on Knowledge (Predictor) and Attitude (Outcome)

Mean difference (Cohen's d)/ Pearson Correlation = 0.47

Regression = Y = a + bX;

Y = dependent variable (Outcome) = Attitude

X = independent variable (predictator) = Knowledge

a = intercept value of X and Y

b = regression co-efficiency slop by 1 unit

b = r (SDy)/ (SDx)

r = Pearson correlation, SDy = standard deviation for variable 1 (knowledge) and SDx = standard deviation for variable 2 (attitude)

b = -0.39 meaning that for every 1 unit increase in knowledge risky behaviour decrease by 0.39 points.

a = 4.30, Therefore; Y = a +bx = 4.30- 0.39

Regression Model Summary:

Knowledge and Attitude towards health risks associated with sachet water consumption

Variables	Value
R	-0.47
R ²	0.22
Adjusted R ²	0.21
Standard Error	0.70

Key: R = Correlation coefficient, R² = Proportion of variance explained, Adjusted R² = Corrected R² for sample size and Standard Error = Accuracy of predictions.

The regression model shows a moderate negative relationship ($R = -0.47$) between knowledge and attitude, indicating that higher knowledge is associated with safer attitudes toward sachet water consumption. With an R^2 of 0.22, the model explains 22% of the variation in students' attitudes, suggesting that knowledge is a meaningful but not sole predictor of their health-related behaviors

ANOVA on Knowledge and Attitude towards health risks associated with sachet water consumption

Sources	SS	Df	Ms	F	Sig
Regression	48.8	1	48.4	100.35	P <0.001
Residual	172.6	358	0.48		
Total	221.0	359			

Key: SS =Sum of squares (variation), df = Degree of Freedom, MS = Mean square, F = F-statistic for significance, p = Probability Value, and Residual = Unexplained variation.

The ANOVA result shows that the regression model predicting students' attitudes from their knowledge is highly significant ($F = 100.35$, $p < 0.001$), meaning knowledge has a statistically meaningful effect on attitude toward health risks associated with sachet water consumption. This indicates that the variation explained by knowledge (48.8) is substantially greater than unexplained variation, confirming that knowledge is a strong predictor of students' attitudes.

Co-efficiency Table

Predicator(Knowledge)	B	Standard Error	Beta	t	Sig
Constant	4.30	0.20		21.5	P <0.001
Knowledge	-0.39	0.04	-0.47	-10.0	P <0.001

Key: B = Actual amount attitude changes when knowledge increases by 1 unit, Beta =Strength and direction of the relationship after standardizing variables (Shows effect size) and Standard Error = How accurate or stable the B value is. Lower = better.

The coefficient table shows that knowledge significantly predicts students' attitudes toward sachet water consumption, with a negative B value (-0.39) indicating that higher knowledge leads to lower risky attitudes ($t = -10.0$, $p < 0.001$). The constant (4.30) and the highly significant p-values confirm that the regression model is strong and reliable, while the Beta value (-0.47) shows a moderate negative effect of knowledge on attitude.

Discussion

One of the findings of this study reveals that Students possess a low level of knowledge on the health risks associated with sachet water. This finding is in consonant with Edeh (2021) report, which suggests that students possess low knowledge on health risk of diseases, including sachet water consumption-related diseases. In support of this, Obodo (2023) showed that secondary school students possess a low level of knowledge on the health issues. However, Sridhar, Okareh and Mustapha (2020) did not support this finding by suggesting that the level of understanding of health risk associated with water consumption may be fairly good in Nigeria. Nevertheless, the low level of knowledge of health risk associated with sachet water consumption did not come as a surprise to the researcher because the consumption of sachet water is prevalent in the study area, suggesting

that individuals had very high conviction on the purity and safety of sachet water consumption. The research hopes that this finding could act as a wakeup call to students to ensure that the sachet water being consumed is safe for drinking. Indeed, the researcher is aware that it is impossible for sachet water consumers to measure the purity of sachet water. However, the study suggests the need to choose alternate source of water such as bottled water or spring water, if they are assessed to consumers as they are safer for consumption.

The study also found that students in the Enugu Education Zone had a poor attitude toward health risks associated with sachet water consumption. Okeh (2021) supported this findings, revealing that the poor water sanitation practice suggests that students had a poor attitude towards health risk associated with water consumption, including sachet water. In addition, Onwumere (2023) supports this finding by highlighting that the attitude of most Nigerian toward sachet water consumption was very poor. World Health Organization (2017) supports this finding by suggesting that the high prevalence of water-related diseases among students underscores their attitude towards the health risk of water consumption, including sachet water consumption. The researcher was not surprised by the findings because secondary school students are adolescents and hence accustomed to numerous health risk behavior. Therefore, it is imperative that the health risk of sachet water consumption is appropriately communicated so that secondary school students do not exaggerate the existing health risk associated with the production and storage of sachet water during consumption.

Conclusions

The study concluded that there was low level of knowledge regarding the health risks associated with sachet water consumption among students and this low knowledge significantly influences their attitudes, as evidenced by the moderate negative relationship and regression results showing that higher knowledge is associated with safer behaviors. Hence, it is hoped that related stakeholders will endorse conservative efforts to alleviate this health issue.

Implications to Emerging Trends and Sustainable Development Goals

The study possess numerous implications for emerging trends and sustainable goals, and it highlights the need for improvement in secondary schools health education programmes. The study showed that it is important to increase students' knowledge on the health risks of consuming sachet water by equipping them with the necessary information to make informed decisions with regards sachet water consumption. In addition, the study underscored the need to improve current health policies and regulations regarding sachet water production and distribution, which may result in improvements in sachet water standards, production and packaging practices. Furthermore, this study contributed to a broader understanding of public health issues related to water consumption by showing the numerous dangers of sachet water consumption and the pathetic nature of individual knowledge and attitude on the health risk associated with sachet water consumption. This may lead to further research and investments in innovative solutions for providing vulnerable communities with safer and more affordable drinking water. With regards to sustainable development goals, this study affirms the importance of ensuring access to clean and safe drinking water for all by highlighting the relationship between health, education, and environmental sustainability, which are prerequisite for achievement sustainable

development goals. This study could lead to awareness, action, and collaboration among stakeholders, including government bodies, educational institutions, and public health organizations, to address the health risks associated with sachet water consumption and work towards achieving the sustainable development goals.

Recommendations

The researcher recommends the following;

1. Students should be educated on the importance of safe water consumption to improve their knowledge of unsafe sachet water.
2. The parent-teachers association should be used as a medium to educate parents on the dangers of sachet water consumption so that they can utilize alternative sources of water that may be safer for consumption.

REFERENCES

- Aladeniyi, K., Olowookere, C. J.Khandaker, M. U.& Alsufyani, S. J. (2022). Evaluation of Radiological Health Risks in Popularly Consumed Brands of Sachet Water in Nigeria. *Front Public Health*.10: 917422.
- Ajzen, I. (2019). Attitudes. In *The Corsini Encyclopedia of Psychology*. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119080708.wbepa42>
- Coffey, P. (2017). *Epistemology; Or the Theory of Knowledge: An Introduction to General Metaphysics*. London: Longman.
- Ede, D, (2021). Knowledge of corona virus among Secondary School Students in Nkanu West Local Government Area of Enugu State. An unpublished report submitted to the Department of Human Kinetics and Health Education, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, ESUT.
- Emerenini, J. (2020). Borehole Water and Sachet Water Production in Southeast Nigeria. A published Dissertation Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the Degree of Doctor of Philosophy Public Health.
- Hassan, A. S., Musa, H, J.,& Mohammed, I. U. (2016). An overview of water supply infrastructural challenges in Nigeria: a case study of Taraba State. *IOSR J Mech Civil Engng*. 2016;13(1):46–51.
- İnceoğlu, M. (2010). *Attitude Perception Communication*. Fifth Edition. İstanbul: Beykent University Publishing House
- Kusa, R.& Williams, K. J. (2022). Evaluating the portability and human health risk of sachet water in Wukari, Nigeria. *Archives of Environmental and Occupational Health*, 78 (2): 71-79

- Miner, C. A, Tagurum, Y. O., Hassan. Z., Afolaranmi. T. O., Bello, D. A., Dakhin, A.&Zoakah, A. I. (2016). Sachet Water: Prevalence of Use, Perception and Quality in a Community of Jos South Local Government Area of Plateau State. *Jos Journal of Medicine*, 9(1): 1-8
- Nnaji, O (2021). Knowledge of Covid-19 preventive protocol among secondary school students in Nkanu West LGA. A Paper Presented In National Conference, Nigeria Association of Physical Education, Health Education, Recreation, Sport and Dance (NAPHR-SD).
- Nwokolo, C (2023). The Negative Health Effects of Sachet Water in Nigeria. Healthguide.ng. <https://healthguide.ng/health-effects-sachet-water-nigeria/>
- Ojekunle, Z. O, Ojekunle, V. O, Eruola, A. O, Oyebanji, F. F, Olatunde, K. A, Amujo, B. T, Sangowusi, O. R., Adekitan, A. A. & Taiwo, A. G. (2015). The Effects of Storage on Sachet Water Quality in Ogun State, Nigeria. *J. Appl. Sci. Environ. Manage.* 19 (2): 183 – 189
- Okeh C. N., (2021). Water sanitation practices among secondary school students in Nkanu West LGA. An unpublished Project Report presented to the Department Of Health and Physical Education Faculty of Education, Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT).
- Onwumere, O. (2023). Sachet Water as a Threat to Public Health; HEALTH & WELLBEING. <https://www.thisdaylive.com/index.php/2016/05/20/sachet-water-as-a-threat-to-public-health>
- Popkin, B. M., D'Anci, K.E. & Rosenberg, I.H. (2010). Water, hydration, and health. *Nutrition Reviews*, 68(8), 439-458.
- Premium Times (2021). Over 26.5 million Nigerian children vulnerable to water-related diseases – UNICEF. <https://www.premiumtimesng.com/news/more-news/450463-over-26-5-million-nigerian-children-vulnerable-to-water-related-diseases-unicef.html?tztc=1>
- Rosenstock, I. M. (1974). Historical origins of the health belief model. *Health Education Monographs*, 2, 328-335
- Sridhar, M. K. C, Okareh, O. T. & Mustapha, M. (2020). Assessment of Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices on Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene in Some Selected LGAs in Kaduna State, Northwestern Nigeria. *J Environ Public Health*.6532512. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7479483/>
- United Nations Children Development Fund (UNICEF) (2023). The Sustainable Development Goals: Halfway to 2030. <https://www.unicef.org/>

Water Science School (2019). The Water in You: Water and the Human Body. United States Geological Survey. <https://www.usgs.gov/special-topics/water-science-school/science/water-you-water-and-human-body>.

World Health Organization (2018). Health through safe drinking water and sanitation. Available from: URL: http://www.who.int/water_sanitation_health/mdg1/en/. (Accessed 18 Aug, 2023).

World Health Organization, (2017). Guidelines for Drinking-Water Quality: Fourth edition incorporating the first addendum. World Health Organisation, Geneva, Switzerland

Wright, J., Dzodzomenyo, M., Fink, G., Wardrop, N. A., Aryeetey, G. Y., Adanu, R. M. & Hill, A. G (2016). Subsidized sachet water to reduce diarrheal disease in young children: a feasibility study in Accra, Ghana. *Am J Trop Med Hyg.*95(1): 239–246.

Zumdahl, S. S. (2020). Water. Encyclopedia Britannica. Retrieved from <https://www.britannica.com/science/water>